

EXPERIENCES AND SUGGESTIONS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL PRINCIPALS' SELECTION IN BARMM: BASIS FOR POLICY FORMULATION

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ABSTRACT

This research attempts to formulate policy by investigating and comparing the perceptions and suggestions on the hiring process used in selecting secondary principals in Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). Employing a comparative-qualitative approach, this study purposively sampled thirty-six (36) secondary principals and two (2) Human Resource (HR) personnel from Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education (MBHTE) and Mindanao State University (MSU) - System Basic Education Unit. The data was collected through in-depth-interview and document analysis and were analyzed through content analysis after transcribing and coding process by the MaxQDA software. The findings disclose both sets of principals have positive and negative perceptions about the process, positive because they deem the procedures to be good or perfect, yet negative because of some factors that tend to influence or manipulate the selection process and decision making. Thus, they suggested a strict adherence to the guidelines in the selection process, avoid the *Palakasan* system or political involvement, and underscore the need to select principals who took on the role of being an Office-in-Charge, Teacher-in-Charge, or Assistant Principal because of their relevant experience managing a school. From these findings, this study formulated a policy that is more comprehensive, updated, and at the same time, contextualized to the needs of the principals in the region of BARMM.

Keywords: *Educational Administrators, Human Resource Management, Merit Based Promotion, Seniority Based Promotion.*

INTRODUCTION

In every learning institution, there is always a leader who is tasked to manage, supervise, and manage the team or the organization as a whole. In the basic education, the school principals or school heads are the main focal persons who lead the school to its success in all of its aspects. The principals serve as leaders for students' learning. In addition, they must know everything from academic contents and pedagogical techniques to human resources management to effectively realize their mandates.

According to the Institute for Educational Leadership (2000), principals must have strong autonomy and authority to pursue various techniques in achieving good outcomes. Hence, it is important to carefully choose a school leader because a school has unique context compare to other organizations. It involves handling stakeholders, teaching and learning process and managing manpower. Therefore, the process of recruiting, hiring, or promoting an employee or a teacher to become a principal is a crucial process in any educational institution. The hiring process is the procedure on how the administrators evaluate and screen their employees through merit for every respected department in order to achieve the desired goals of the school. As Victoria State Government (2020) claimed, the prime asset of an organization is the people or the new employees recruited who represent a great investment of time and effort. Moreover, the value represented by selecting the right employee for the position can be found in higher performance, increased team morale and increased productivity. In fact, Section 2(2), Article IX(B) of the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines provides that appointments in the Civil Service shall be made only according to merit and fitness (Llego, 2023). Moreover, Donaldson (2011) stressed that principals arguably play the most important role in ensuring that excellent teaching occurs in their school. The role of the principal extends beyond the people in the school to include the school plant and funding. Thus, hiring the right principal can lead to quality education and a progressive community. Similarly, AISheihhi and Alzouebi (2020) mentioned that school principals play a vital role in the development of education in any country.

Consequently, various studies on hiring school principals in other countries were conducted to help an organization in recruiting, hiring, and promoting school principals. Khumalo (2021) found that their hiring process in South Africa needs more equitable and transparent system on the inequities in principal selection which tends to perpetuate socio-economic disparities. Aravena (2020) also identified that lacking consistency and transparency in principal selection processes across South American country. Moreover, there are lack of professional standards, closed-merit-selection policy, lack of preparation training, lack of partnership among the institutions, ineffective selection strategies, irrelevant professional courses for principals, and infrequent assessment and evaluation for principals (Aziz & Quraishi, 2016). In Qatar, there is a need for more focused leadership skills and qualities (Romanowski et al., 2019). Moreover, in USA, principal

selection is both fair and foul depending upon the locale (Palmer & Mullooly, 2015). Meanwhile, in the Philippines, the BARMM's hiring process is not free from problems. Casil (2021) indicates that the recruitment is challenged by lack of qualified applicants. Aside from scarcity of fit civil servants, the hiring process is also challenged by favoritism, nepotism, and patronage politics, which distort the merit-based hiring system. Furthermore, there is a lack of media platforms in some provinces like that of Sulu which can be used to publish vacancies of the Division (Satul, 2001).

While reviewing the related studies indicated in this paper, it showed that most of studies were conducted outside the Philippines. These studies were conducted using case studies, comparative, mapping, literature reviews, conceptual arguments, and systematic reviews. Some of these studies also utilized mixed methods or qualitative studies, whereas in the Philippines, most studies were quantitative in design and that studies on hiring process dealt only on employees in and none specifically for principals. In this case, it appears that little research was done using qualitative approach investigating the hiring process of principals for they were the most important stakeholders in the community.

Due to the sensitive nature of the topic—which is how they are promoted or designated as secondary principals—this present study requires a qualitative methodology. In such instance, examining the actual circumstances within the BARMM requires a close examination of the participants' genuine and thorough viewpoints. This time, the researcher wanted to know what was actually going on throughout the hiring process because it is impossible to generalize the findings in this case. Because the majority of the prior research on hiring selection in this region employed quantitative studies that generalized the opinions of a large number of participants, this study requires to know the precise viewpoints from the participants.

Despite bearing the name “Bangsamoro,” the region needs to be globally competitive, and the idea that “No Bangsamoro Child Left Behind” needs to be upheld or improved. This was accomplished by looking into the selection process of principals and how they came to be chosen as leaders, since they were the father or mother in molding youngsters within the community. As Meador (2019) postulated that the roles of the principal cover many different areas including leadership, teacher evaluation, and student discipline; above all, a good principal is balanced within the roles and works hard to ensure that this principal is doing the best for all constituents involved.

The significance of this study is to provide an insight regarding selection process of the secondary principals and these opinions became the basis for formulating a policy in the selection of principals in the context of the BARMM region. Selecting principal is crucial to consider all concerns regarding hiring selection as they are the most significant stakeholders within a school or department. These individuals play a crucial role in achieving the educational goals of the Department of Education by managing, supervising, and guiding learners and teachers in daily activities. This study aimed at establishing clear criteria for the selection process, including a requirement for the itemized secondary principals for the BARMM - Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical

Education (MBHTE) and designated principals from the Mindanao State University system. This study focused on secondary school principals as they have greater autonomy in their schools compared to elementary principals, who are still supervised by the district supervisor.

Moreover, since MSU System Basic Education Units consists of Community high Schools, the researcher chose only the high schools from MBHTE to maintain its consistency and because MBHTE secondary and elementary schools have the same general process in terms of hiring principals. Hence, the main goal of this research is to formulate policy in hiring or selection procedure by investigating the experiences of the secondary principals on how they were promoted, designated, recruited, or selected as school principals. In order to replicate actual circumstances in the selection of principals in this area, the hiring procedures of two organizations - the MBHTE school principals and the MSU System Basic Unit school principals were compared in this study and the findings were used in formulating policy.

Research Questions

More specifically, this research investigated and compared the experiences and perception of secondary school principals' selection used in hiring secondary principals as well as the common practices for selecting, particularly secondary school principals from MBHTE and MSU System Basic Education Units. The following are the specific research questions that this study sought to investigate:

1. How is the process for selecting principals perceived by the secondary school principals and human resource personnel of:
 - 1.1 MSU – SBSE,
 - 1.2 BARMM – BSE
2. What suggestions for the improvement of the selection process could be drawn from the secondary school principals and human resource personnel of:
 - 2.1 MSU – SBSE,
 - 2.2 BARMM – BSE.
3. What policy of selection process could be formulated based on the findings of this study?

METHODOLOGY

Research locale

Since the employment process is centralized and overseen by the regional office, the researcher focused on a specific region because the topic pertains to the selecting process of principals. Thus, this study was undertaken in Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), specifically the five provinces handled by the Secondary Education of Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education (MBHTE) and the Mindanao State University - System Basic Education Units. Since this dissertation

discusses principal selection, it is best to look into this procedure throughout the entire region because they are responsible in recruiting employees. Officially known as BARMM, the Bangsamoro Autonomous territory in Muslim Mindanao is an administrative territory in the Philippines that is part of the Mindanao Island group. It encompasses the provinces of Tawi Tawi, Sulu, Maguindanao, Lanao del Sur, and Basilan. (Philatlas, 2023). On the other hand, MSU campuses from BARMM are MSU Main Campus (Marawi City, Lanao del Sur), MSU-Maguindanao (Dinaig, Maguindanao), MSU-Sulu (Jolo, Sulu), and MSU-TCTO (Bongao, Tawi-Tawi) (Mindanao State University, 2013).

Sampling Procedures

The researcher used purposive sampling to gather principals' perceptions and suggestions in hiring selection, focusing on school heads who have undergone the selection process. Moreover, this study utilized a comparative-qualitative approach. As Creswell and Creswell (2018) explained, qualitative research is an approach used to explore and understand the meaning that individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. Therefore, this study requires a qualitative approach due to the sensitive nature of the topic, which is how secondary principals are designated or promoted. In such instance, examining the actual circumstances within the BARMM requires a close examination of the participants' real and thorough viewpoints.

Participants

The participants in this study were the secondary school principals and human resources personnels from the MBHTE-BARMM and from MSU – System Basic Education Units. Due to the lack of MSU community high schools, there were thirty-six (36) secondary principals overall who had gone through the hiring procedure during their time at the BARMM, as opposed to fifty (50) secondary principals instead. Additionally, at least two (2) human resources personnel to confirm the principals' opinions, if they aligned. Originally, five principals would be selected from each province, namely the Province of Lanao del Sur, Maguindanao, Basilan, Sulo, and Tawi-Tawi. However, this was not followed due to some circumstances, such as their unavailability and refusal to participate. In more detail, the provinces like Basilan, Sulu, and Tawi-Tawi (BASULTA) have few itemized principals (MBHTE) and no community high schools (MSU); for this reason, the researcher decided to complete the participants to the largest or mainland of the BARMM, the Maguindanao and Lanao del Sur province. The data presented in Table 1 is based on the record from MBHTE planning for the academic year 2022-2023.

As can be gleaned on the Table 1, the MSU-System Basic Education Units has twenty school principals and only eleven (11) principals were able to participate due its limited high schools. These eleven respondents are enough since the target respondents in qualitative study should be at least five to twenty-five respondents; as Teacher Ryan affirmed this by mentioning that Creswell (2007) suggested that researchers interview with five to twenty-five people who have all personally encountered the occurrence. After all, there are a total of thirty-eight (38) responses to this dissertation. The Table 1 is the number of secondary principals who joined in the interview process.

Table 1. The Number of Secondary Principals who Joined in The Interview Process

	Province	Target Participants	Number of High Schools	Participated Principals
MSU – System Basic Education Units	Lanao del Sur (Excluding Lanao del Norte)	5	9	5
	Maguindanao	5	1	1
	Tawi-Tawi	5	19	5
	Sulo (Declined)	5	1	0
	TOTAL	20	31	11
MBHTE – Secondary Basic Education	I. Lanao del Sur	5	64	
	a. Lanao del Sur I		23	5
	b. Lanao del Sur II		37	1
	c. Marawi City		4	2
	II. Maguindanao	5	18	
	a. Maguindanao II		13	4
	b. Cotabato City Division		5	4
	III. Basilan	5	5	3
	IV. Tawi-Tawi	5	7	4
	V. Sulo	5	6	2
TOTAL	25	100	25	
Grand Total		45		36

Data Gathering Procedure

In this study, the primary data were collected through in-depth interviews of the 36 secondary principals selected from the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). Cresswell and Poth (2018) adapted list of qualitative data collection sources; one of the listed data collections is the interview, which conducted on one-on-one interviews in the same room or virtually via web page or e-mail platforms and conducted focus group interview in the same room, or virtually via web page or e-mail platforms. Prior to collecting the required data, the participants' in-depth interview schedules were set up with their approval. Provinces that were physically difficult to reach due to distance and security concerns, like Tawi-Tawi, Sulu, and Basilan, were interviewed virtually via video conferencing platforms or over the phone. The interview process for the closest provinces, like Lanao del Sur and Maguindanao, involved one-on-one in-person interviews.

Moreover, to ensure internal validity, triangulation of data was collected through multiple sources to include two sets of interviews and document analysis (Creswell &

Cresswell, 2018). Data triangulation was utilized to validate the experiences of the secondary principals. Thus, the official documents guidelines regarding selection criteria (BOR (Board of Regents) Resolution N. 149. Series 1997 and National Guidelines were analyzed as one of the secondary data collected; then, a follow up verification from the MBHTE-HRMD Board Officials and MSU-System Basic Education Unit Committee was done to consult if there are another guidelines, policies, rules, and regulations.

Research Instruments

Mack et al. (2005) explained the strength of qualitative research is the ability to provide complex textual descriptions of how people experience a given research issue. Moreover, it provides information about “human” side of an issue – that is, the often-contradictory behaviors, beliefs, opinions, emotions, and relationships of individuals. Thus, this study is a plain qualitative approach due to having two instruments used. In this case, the researcher used one of the common qualitative methods as the main instrument of the study: the in-depth-interview of two set of respondents which are the thirty-six (36) secondary principals and two (2) human resource personnel, and document analysis of guidelines in hiring procedure which is other data gathering methods to verify the opinions of the participants. Moreover, this study includes the observation of hiring procedure of each organization; however, this was not completed due to its unavailability and confidentiality. Certainly, the interview questions were accumulated from the related literature of the study which have great connection in the problem encountered in the local setting of the researcher. In each question, there are guided questions or sub-questions as approach when the interview process is suddenly goes off its issues. Also, the hiring procedures of the two groups were analyzed to ascertain if the perspectives of the two participant sets aligned with the documents such as the BOR Resolution No. 149. s. 1997 and certain national directives (DepEd Order No. 39 s. 2007, DO No. 42 s. 2007, DO No. 19 s. 2016, DO No. 41 s. 2016, DO No. 024 s. 2020, and National Qualifying Examination for School Heads (NQESH)).

The process of analysis

The data was analyzed using the steps of Marguerite et al. (2006) and MaxQDA software. The researcher manually transcribed interviews and coded the data, but still manually checked for accuracy. The following were the steps used by the researcher to analyze the data: (1) Preparing and Organizing the Data; (2) Reviewing and Exploring the Data; (3) Coding Data into Categories; (4) Constructing Descriptions of People, Places, and Activities; (4) Building Categories; and (5) Reporting and Interpreting Data.

The scope and Limitations

Again, this focused on the experiences of secondary school principals during their hiring selection as principal applicants in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), specifically the Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education (MBHTE) and the Mindanao State University-System Basic Education Units (MSU-SBEU). The study involved selecting five secondary school principals from each province: namely, Lanao del Sur, Maguindanao, Basilan, Sulu, and Tawi-Tawi. As a whole, the

study selected at least fifty (50) secondary schools within the region; twenty-five (25) secondary school principals each from MBHTE as well as in the MSU System Basic Education Units. However, this was not followed due to some limitations.

In MBHTE, there are provinces that were not able to participate during the interview due to their unavailability. Nevertheless, because there were at least two or more participants as representatives from each province, those who failed to participate were able to compensate or replaced by principals from other provinces. As to the MSU-System Basic Education Units' campuses within the BARMM, only the Lanao del Sur and Tawi-Tawi have System Basic Education Units and these provinces completed the five participants for each province. Further, other MSU campuses that have laboratory schools are the MSU Maguindanao and MSU Sulu, none from MSU Basilan. These MSU campuses that have their own integrated laboratory school were included in the target participants, however, from these schools that were contacted, only the MSU Maguindanao accepted the invitation to participate in the study.

A limitation of the study is that only secondary principals from MSU System Basic Education Units and from MBHTE were considered as participants, as well as one Human Resource Personnel from each institution. The Elementary or Senior High Principals are not included. Additionally, the topic of the study is sensitive, and it may be challenging for the researcher to convince principals to reveal their experiences during the hiring process. Except the Board or committee of the HRMD, the study did not include minister, director general, superintendents, and other educational administrators, as there have been various changes in educational administrators in the region for approximately nine years. Overall, the study focused solely on the experiences of principals during their hiring process and selection as a basis for formulating policy regarding hiring selection.

RESULTS

1. Perception of the Principal Selection Process

1.1. Perception of Group A – MSU-System Basic Education Unit

This group produced three categories of their sentiments, these are *Consistent Good Hiring procedures (21)*, *Effective and High Performing Unit due to Constituents (5)*, *Nomination and Replacement Process (4)*, Whereas on the other the Human Resources personnel have one category *Best Process*.

The participants perceived that the hiring process in MSU system basic education unit follows a consistent process in accordance with the guidelines from BOR. This is evident with the way the search committee only looks into the most qualified principals based on their selection criteria. Also, these principals mentioned that they must undergo presenting their concept papers, and that they must submit school credentials and many others. According to M8, the procedures are good because it is not something that were drafted in just one day but took extensive days to plan and design. Moreover, the participants claimed that behind the high performing unit is the deeper dedication of

the principals, and how productive they are. Community has great impact in the effectiveness of such unit because they considered the linkages as part of their learning process. As to their teachers and other employees, they were guided actually on what is the best thing to do in the field, and that their constituents have full respect to their principals. For example, M1 perceived the effectiveness of the hiring process because it involves the community and its constituents which is one of the best considerations in promoting principals in the MSU-SBEU. At least one excerpt is displayed for this claimed: (Note: Excerpt number is based on the order number from dissertation)

Excerpt 107: *Ok... I think effective naman siya... kasi we consider the community... the clients... the students... ok kung saan community mayron sila at kung saan sila naka-resides in community... and then... I think effective naman... kasi ang number one dito... you can manage... there are qualified to manage the principal director of the department...qualification wise... academically wise... but in terms of actual management... so nagkakakroon ng problema... kailangan talaga 'yong... not necessarily na dadaan pa sa... what I mean is... the protocol... the procedural way of... which is dapat naman talaga... but since... in a way... mayroon naman talagang ahmm out of the listings... as I have told you while ago... from the listings na... uy... hindi na kailangan natin magpatawag pa ng...from the enumerated names... they can decide... kung sinong puwedi... 'yon ang nagiging process dito...*

yeah... yeah... any way nasabi natin maganda... kasi... alhamdulillah... effective naman... Effective naman siya... kasi kung ineffective siya... definitely hindi ganoon ang... hindi kailangan ng another procedure... or process... (M1)

(Ok... I think it is effective... because we consider the community... the clients... the students... ok which community do they have and where do they reside in community... and then... I think it is effective... because the number one here... you can manage... there are qualified to manage the principal director of the department... qualification wise... academically wise... but in terms of actual management... so there is problem... It is really necessary the... not necessarily that you must undergo in that... what I mean is... the protocol... the procedural way of... which is... it really must be... but since... in a way... there are really... ahmm out of the listings... as I have told you while ago... from the listings... hey... that we don't need to call more... from the enumerated names... they can decide if who can... that is the process here...

yeah... yeah... anyway, we said it, it was beautiful... because... alhamdulillah... It is effective... It is really effective... because if it's ineffective... definitely, that's not the... not needed another procedure... or process... (M1))

Lastly, Nomination and Replacement Process talks about how principals can be nominated and replaced. Nomination is done by the chancellor through qualified applicants or among peers; and there are cases that there are no qualified candidates

who meet the criteria. Nevertheless, their colleagues may nominate one of them to be the aspirants. But still, even if the applicant has no contender, the same process will have to be applied. Say for instance, M4 believed that replacement of principal after the term of president is better than being full-pledge or itemized principal as Department of Education (DepEd) usually do, because she believed that if the performance of principal is not good, there are actually nominees in the units as replacements.

Excerpt 110: *So sii raknun na... type akn anan a till retirement ogaid na simpre paka-retire ta bu oh? Na khapakay mambo uto... opama na... o daa... o di na o di nga kabaya gyuto a principal na... so mga decision nka na ago mga bright ideas ka nabgawn nkawn badn...a tigka kataay gyaie suwaangka... ogopingka badn skaniyan... ka nainu ka khadaon bu ka bawn ine tyutok... so sii raknun mambo gyanan a sa DepEd... (R: oway adn pn a MOOE iran...) oway gyuto... kay adn man mambo a usually ah di penggalebek kay lagid uto a nainu ka myatutok ako run bu... pero so sii raknun na sakto rakn uto a lagiduto a imanto na aya president na 6 years na after 6 years na o di mapiya so performance angkoto a principal na khapakay a palitan... na o mapiya na remain... (M4)*

(As for me... I do like that until retirement but of course you will be retired anyway... that is possible also (until retirement)... if you didn't like her... just give her your decision and bright ideas... (saying) "just do this, so and so..." just help her for she won't last there (soon to retire) as for me in the DepEd... (R: they have also MOOE) yes, that's it... actually there is usually who won't do his work properly because anyway, he is already there as full-pledge... however, as for me, it's ok with me (in MSU) now that the president is in 6 years (term) then, after 6 years if the performance of principal is not good, he can be replaced... then, if it is good, (just let him) be remained... (M4))

1.2. Perception of Group B – MBHTE

The following were the categories found; *There is a Fair Process (19), Delayed Hiring Process (11), Empowerment of Principal by Prioritizing Volunteer Teachers as well as Hiring and Promoting Teachers (11), Considering Division Level of Selecting principals and Teachers (11), BARMM Decides Everything (9), Inconsistency of Hiring and Manipulation of the Process (9), Prioritizing OIC or who Managed School already (8), Imposing Transparency (6), Hardship of being OIC (5), Filling in the Vacant Items Immediately (4)*, whereas on the HR personnel, only one category formed regarding hiring process, which is the *Existing Smooth Process*.

The participants shared that the process is fair and just for all applicants. This means that the selection process is based on merit and qualification based upon the pertinent papers endorsed to the panel committee. Additionally, some participants highlighted that there is a delay in the hiring process. Likewise, some principals suggested that divisions or schools should be empowered in terms of hiring and promoting teachers because only each respective schools or divisions who are well-aware of their needs. This is also to avoid hiring or choosing an applicant that does not match the need of the

school. Furthermore, the principals also mentioned the need to prioritize volunteer teachers in terms of hiring because they knew their sacrifices and efforts. In this case, at least let them recommend whom they wanted to be their teachers and these recommended teachers must have transparency record about their ranking in the school level. At least one excerpt is displayed for this claimed:

Excerpt 117: *Opinion ko jan actually... dapat ibalik ang dating process... ma-abolish a giya a kwan... tunaa uto ba... giya a centralization... at tsaka... dati talaga is magsisimula sa division office... ka alam nila... sila 'yong direct nag-su-supervise sa mga principal sa field... ang superintendent talaga ang nag-su-supervise... kasi alam nila kung sino 'yong mga working principal... at tsaka... sino 'yong mga deserving... kagya pakasung ko mga eskuwelaan... phkailay niyan... tunaa ie paras o physical appearance o school... so actual number of students... oway... so mga teacher... at tsaka... sii sa DepEd guideline of hiring na gyuto... ang division office... ka aya bu man a sangan ah region na processing... unless... a adn a myagprotest... a tig iran a mya biased so recruitment selection so sa division office... na ruo phagapas sa region a protest niyan gyuto a certain a kuwan a di magagaw... so dapat... ang sa akin na ibalik na lng 'yon... para ibarat o maka kasoy anan... na ba unda anan a isa a paka-ugop a kha-minimize a giya mga delayed a processing sii sa region... ka inu siran phka-delayed ka everything na sisii kiran... hiring and everything... gyanan a dapat a mga TACE... mga demo na saya bu anan sa division office... kasi ang nasa standard sa guidelines for hiring recruitment... specially like sa Teacher I... na it will start from the school.... Why? Because the school who identify ko needs iyan... like sii rktano sii sa high school... na andamanaya ie kakhatokawi run a region a aya kailangan tano na Math major... (P24)*

(My opinion there actually... the previous process must be returned... this (centralization) must be abolished... what's this... this centralization... and then... before actually we had started in the division office... because they knew... they are the one who supervised the principals in the field... the superintendent is the one who really supervise... because they knew the working principal... and... who are the deserving... because s/he has been roving around the schools... s/he has seen it... of what the form or physical appearance of school... the actual number of students... yes... the teachers... Aside from that... in the DepEd guideline of hiring...that's it actually... the division office... the only task given to the region is processing... unless... if there are protest... that they said that the division office are biased in their recruitment selection... then, they will go to the region and they will protest that there were contenders who have been competing... so, it must be... as for me, they must return the (decentralization)... if this has been returned... maybe this is one of the aid to minimize the delayed processing in the region... they have been experiencing delayed because everything is in their hands... the hiring and everything... actually, those TACE... demonstrations... must be in the division office... because the standard in guidelines for hiring recruitment...

specially like in Teacher I... it will start from the school.... Why? Because the school is the one who identify its needs... like in ours in high school... how will the region know that our need is Math major? (P24))

Moreover, the principals thought that everything is controlled and decided by the BARMM. The principals elaborated on the idea that BARMM decides everything. For example, P9 said that cronyism exist wherein if they have strong backer and they are close to them, then, they can be promoted. Furthermore, the participants disclosed that there were applicants who were promoted without going through the process like managing a school, while the unqualified ones got the position. In this case, *Prioritizing OIC or who Managed School Already* should be followed. It can be said that educational attainment alone is not sufficient to be qualified, unless the applicants have related experience in managing a school. Due to the existence of nepotism or cronyism, some principals perceived the need to impose transparency in the process. P10 shared her perceptions that the results in the hiring of principals should be posted and made public for the applicants to see, this is to eliminate any thoughts of rigged or manipulated results. Lastly, the participants believed that not filling the vacancy immediately will affect the Bangsamoro learners. According to P23, the motto “No Bangsamoro Learners will Be Left Behind” cannot be achieved if the MBHTE neglects to fill in the vacant positions immediately. P17 disclosed that there were principals who claimed to have teachers’ deficiency, while having more or less eighty students in just one section. Thus, for them, no matter how knowledgeable the assigned teacher in that section, it will be difficult to meet the learning objectives and needs of the students. So, one excerpt is displayed for this claimed:

Excerpt 133: *Much better... kung may natural vacancies... mas Maganda talaga na fill up immediately... kasi as per experience namin noon... hindi pa kame under sa ARMM... under sa region... matagal ng one month... publication tapos fill up-an kaagad... kawawa kasi ang learners... anyway may allocation naman ie... nadyan naman sa DBM naman ei... may annual budget naman ie...*

hindi nila alam... kahit ang motto na “No Bangsamoro learners will left-behind” hindi nila alam... once hindi nila pinipil-upan ang item... that vacant item that will lead to the Bangsamoro will be left-behind... that is contradict to the motto to the policy... No Bangsamoro learners will be left-behind... once hindi mo pinil-upan ‘yong natural vacancy item... that will lead the Bangsamoro learners na ma left behind... no...? isipin mo... one natural vacancy teacher... in a certain institution... ilang teaching load ang teacher na ‘yon... ok... five teaching loads plus one advisory... kailangan anim teaching load ang teacher... kasi advisory considered as one teaching load... ok... five subject areas ma left behind ng Bangsamoro... isa lang teacher na how many thousand item na hindi na fill up dito sa BARMM. (P23)

(Much better... If there are natural vacancies... It is better to fill this up immediately... because as per our experience before... when we were not yet under in the ARMM... Under the region... it takes a month... the publication then after that It is already filled up immediately... the learners were pitiful on

this matter... anyway, there is an allocation actually... It is in the DBM... There is an annual budget eventually... They don't know... even the motto No Bangsamoro learners will leave behind they don't know... once they don't fill-up the item... that vacant items that will lead to the Bangsamoro will be left-behind... that is contradict to the motto to the policy... No Bangsamoro learners will leavebehind... once the natural item will never be filled up... this will lead the Bangsamoro learners be left behind... right...? think about it... one natural vacancy of teacher... in a certain institution... how many teaching loads is the teacher? Ok... five teaching loads plus one advisory... because the teacher must have six teaching loads... and advisory considered as one teaching load... Ok... five subject areas would be left behind by the Bangsamoro... In just one teacher and how about thousands of items that will not be filled up here in BARMM... (P23))

2. Suggestion on how to Improve the Hiring Selection of Group A – MSU-System Basic Education Unit

2.1. Suggestion on how to Improve the Hiring Selection of Group A – MSU-System Basic Education Unit

With the findings from the principals, there were four categories identified: *Principal empowerment (6)*, *Considering and providing school maintenance (5)*, *Respect and stick to the discretionary power and process (4)*, and *Consideration of some technical requirements (3)*. On the other hand, the HR personnel interviewed did not mention any suggested policies that can be added to the existing process. As HR1 said,

Excerpt 135: *Wala na akong maisip na maidagdag dito kasi this is BOR approved in 1997... so... until now it's not yet amended...(HR1)*

(I can't think of anything else to add (recommendation) to this because it was approved by BOR in 1997... so... until now It is not yet amended... (HR1))

This implies that the BOR is enough for them and very operative process because most of the principals appreciated how the hiring process goes. Principal M8 even claimed that there is nothing to add because for him, everything seems to be already complete. Probably, before the resolution or any policy is accepted and implemented this went a thorough evaluation and systematic review.

The suggestion of the participants to principals should be empowered in their functions is significant for educational policy and practice. Empowering principals can lead to several benefits such as being better equipped to make effective decisions that can enhance overall school performance, including teacher hiring, academic achievement and student outcomes. For them, retired subject teacher must be replaced by a teacher of the same major in order to avoid designating a teacher who is not qualified or is not fit to hold the position in the field. Thus, they suggested the principal empowerment which means allowing the principals to give recommendation as to who can replace him or her because they already know the needed subject teachers; and in

terms of promotion, they already know those proactive teachers who can continue what they started. At least one excerpt is displayed for this claimed:

Excerpt 137: *Kagiya samanaya imanto na so policy a phag-hired... na so... lagid sii a mya-vacant so kuwan amie... myag retire so... one of the faculty of ARPAN teacher retired.... so... kailangan ko ng major in ARPAN na LET passer... opama na so phag retired na MATH majors na MATH major ang ipapalit.... hindi gaya noon a asara myaka graduate ka na pwede ka nang maging teacher... (M2)*

(As of now... the policy of hiring... is that... say for instance, there is a vacant here... someone retired... one of the faculty of ARPAN teacher retired... so... I need the Major in ARPAN who is LET passer... I mean is... if the retired teacher is Math Major, then this must be replaced by the Math major... not unlike before, at least you were graduated then you'll be a teacher... (M2))

Moreover, the principals interviewed communicated their concern of having no Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE). Metaphorically, a person cannot run the car without the fuel; the same goes with identified organization, one cannot fully implement projects or plans without the budget. No matter how good the vision and plan in the presented concept paper, this cannot be fully implemented without resources. Likewise, the participants said that people need to respect the discretionary power of the president whoever he or she designated as principal. This entails that there might be some individuals who tend to complain and/or not satisfied with the chosen principal, however, some participants underscore that the discretionary power of the person in authority, which is the president, is final and must be respected. Lastly, the consideration for some technical requirement pertains to cases wherein there is a petition to replace another principal or a petition to extend the term of a principal. This means that there are situations in which the teachers are not satisfied with designated principals, so they call for petition. At least two excerpts are displayed for this claimed:

Excerpt 141: *Yes... dapat isali kame... sa mga ibinibigay na improvements... tulad ng mga buildings... mga upoan... Mabigyan ng MOOE... Tsaka 'yong pera ng Main-Campus mabigyan ng kahit isa lang building... 'yong Donation na binigay sa kanila... hindi 'yon mabongkag... talagang firm sila na talagang hindi mabongkag... ibig sabhin ng mabongkag na talagang dito na kame... (M3)*

(Yes... we should be included for provided improvements... just like buildings... chairs... They should give us MOOE... And then; the money of Main-Campus, if possible... they should give us of at least one building... The (lot) donation that was given to them... this shouldn't be fallen apart (contracts)... they must be firm that this could not be transgressed... what I mean to say is... we really stay here... (M3))

Excerpt 144: *Dapat na gyanan a mga petition a lagidanan na didn iphag... tunaa inie... (R: entertain...) hnnn... ka simpre... lagid sakn na ibarat o kuwan na mababaas ta malalagoy ka andamanaya ie ka-reach ata ta sa gyuto a goal ta...ago uba adn pn a miuman ta a pinaka-mapiya a goal...*

unfortunately na... adn a phaghatak ka niyan pababa... instead a pagugupan ka niyan so tig akn kiran man uto ah lagid o aya masusuwa tanu sii na lagido mga crab mentality ah...tabiya tig akn man uto ah...instead a iphag push ako niyo pataas na aya siwa iyo na gyamit ako niyo sa baba...ka sa mauna na skano mambo ie pamamanik ruo sa puro... instead a mauuna ako dn uto sa puro na dapat uto na tuwakan ako niyo... ipagpush ako niyo ruo na aya siwa iyo na pagdown ako niyo a tig akn man uto... dadn mambo a khasuwa tano... (R: di kha-achieve so goals...) Gyuto... so sii raknun bu na... once ah... kagya sii rkame sa MSU na discretionary power a president kagya a designation na irespeto kung anu desisyon ng president... (M4)
 (That petition should not be (entertained)... of course... just like me say for instance that I am eagerly to reach my goal (in the school) ... and if there are other best goals that I could add it up... unfortunately... there are (people) who is letting you down instead of helping you... as what I've said to them... we are just like crab mentality, we due respect, instead of pushing me up to success, what you did is you just grab me down... just to be on the top... I was already there on the top; at least, you should have provided me a stair to push me up but then you just let me down that's it... as for me... once (there is a) ... because in MSU, there is a discretionary power of president of this designation; then, let just respect that decision... (M4))

2.2. Suggestion on how to Improve the Hiring Selection of Group B - MBHTE

The following were the identified categories: *Considering Length and Managerial Experience (14)*, *Principal Empowerment (10)*, *Adopting National Guidelines (8)*, *Considering Qualification and Personal Quality (7)*, *Considering Consistency of Process (5)*, *Considering importance of Community Linkages and Practice (4)*. Meanwhile, the HR personnel has only one category, *Power to Endorse by Heads*, this means that the HR suggested that superintendents should be the one to recommend policies since they knew what is happening in the field and that only the Minister has the right to recommend such policy.

The principals suggested to consider length of service of the applicants and should be included in the minimum criteria. They also highlight that the that the committee should promote or prioritize those who have already experienced managing a school because of their experience, the efforts, energy, and resources they have invested for the school. This suggestion from the principals is rooted from their observations or experience of cases when the length of service was not considered in the selection of principal, but other applicants were chosen even if they lack this criterion. Furthermore, they suggested that the selection of principal in MBHTE must be done in the school level or some call this 'localization' because it is the head of the school and the teachers that know what the school specifically needs. That is why they further suggested that the school head should have the power to endorse to the division or to the region a competent and qualified applicant; and the selected qualified applicants can be put in short list or transmittal together with the evaluation ranking sheet. Two excerpts are displayed for this claimed:

Excerpt 146: *Yes... doon sa... committee screening for school heads or principal... dapat maidagdag natin 'yong number of years or length of service... being of an OIC of the school... kasi it's unfair to them all na halimbawa... sabay kayo mag-a-aaply... two years in service versus ikaw 15 years in service as OIC... so idagdag sana nila doon sa criteria nila, sa qualifications nila... na dapat priority 'yong mga tenured na... 'yong mga matagal ng OIC... wag naman 'yong new... sa totoo lang bata pa lang... 'yong iba 20 years ng OIC... so kawawa naman sila no? 'yon lang ang pwede ko maidagdag...(P1)*

(Yes... in... committee screening for school heads or principal... it should be added the number of years or length of service... being of an OIC of the school... because It is unfair to them all, say for instance... you've applied simultaneously... two years in service versus you as 15 years in service as being OIC... so, hoping that this will be added to their criteria... in their qualifications... that the tenured must be the priority... those who have been (in service) for long time as OIC... do not be the new one... actually they are too young for this... then, the others are 20 years being an OIC... so, they are so unfortunate, right? That's all I can add actually... (P1))

Excerpt 151: *Ang ma-i-re-recommend ko sana bibigyan kame ng full implementation of empowerment...as principal... pero... hindi ko na sinabe 'yon kasi pati superintendents...powerless... Yes...Everything is under the control of Sir_____. So... anu 'yong binibigyan nila ng pansin doon...'yon din ang mangyari ma-promote... so... wala kanang magawa...So, it is only by words...You see it by word... You pray from Allah... na someday...somehow... Na mabibigyan ng pusong mamon si Sir_____na bibigyan nya ng pasin 'yong mga principals para 'yong i-re-recruit natin na teacher sa Math na hindi ilagay 'yong nakatapos ng Filipino... ei paano 'yon? Ang school... How can a math teacher teach English and how can English teacher teach Math? misfit talaga... (P9)*

(What I would like to recommend is having a full implementation of empowerment hopefully... as principal... but... I did not even tell this because even the superintendents... powerless.....Yes... Everything is under the control of Sir (Superior's name) ... So... what they've considered there... is what they want to be promoted... so... you can't do anything... So, it is only by words... You see it by word... You pray from Allah... that someday... somehow... that Sir _____ will be given a soft-hearted heart... that he will pay attention to the principals, for what we wanted to recruit is suited to his field, the teacher in Math would not be placed to those who finished in Filipino (major). How is that? The school... how can a math teacher teach English and how can English teach Math?... It is really misfit...(P9))

Also, it should be noted that MBHTE-BARMM follows the policy guidelines in the selection of principal based on the DepEd Order, BARMM also has its own process. However, looking at the experiences of the participants, it appears that this policy is not strictly being followed. Thus, the third category is *Adopting the National Guidelines*, as

some participants suggested that the hiring process under the BARMM must adopt National Guidelines. After all, the criteria must focus more on the qualifications, performance and competence of individuals; and these principals should continue the good policy which they must have adopted to the national guidelines. And as mentioned previously, this performance includes not only their educational qualifications but more so, their managerial experiences. More importantly, these principals suggested for transparency in the policy or hiring in the BARMM. Consistency of process that they suggested includes not accepting late submission of application papers, that the division must be the first to screen the papers and be endorsed the qualified applicants to the region; that the superior must be fair and transparent in hiring, especially for those with administrative function, and more importantly, the *palakasan* system such as kinship or cronyism should be avoided. At least two excerpts are displayed for this claimed:

Excerpt 162: *Mayroon din sa amin dito... na 'yong... matagal na TIC... here comes... nag-apply as principal... ang nakuha 'yong guro niya... kasi may kapatid siyang _____... naka-alis 'yong matagal nang TIC... oo...parang sabe ko... parang... (R: parang disrespectful po din kasi 'yon Sir... kawawa naman 'yong TIC...) kaya nga... paano man yan ei... mag TIC ka tapos guro mo ang naging full-pledge... parang mahiya ka rin... 'yong policy na 'yong malinaw...(P12)*

(We had (experience) it here too... That's the... long-time TIC... here comes... who applied as principal... the one that have been promoted was her teacher... because s/he has sibling _____... The long time TIC was left... yes... and I said... It is like... yes... how is that... You're TIC then the one who is going to be a full-fledged is your teacher... that was so shameful too (in your part) ...the policy must be transparent... (P12))

Excerpt 167: *Yes... once they already made these standard qualifications... dapat number 1 is... they have to count the experience first... and localization... experience... the localization... meaning...when I say experience... kasi... may mga mas bata pa jan... ok naman kahit mas bata as long as qualified... pero may mga mas qualified na mas matagal na sa puwesto... yes... kasi... if you apply the law of localization... walang chance na 'yong school head... pa-out-out kasi taga dyan siya... so pwede niya talaga tingnan 'yong school niya... yong access niya sa community...(P18)*

(Yes... once they already made these these standard qualifications... The number one is... they have to count the experience first... and localization... experience... the localization... meaning... when I say experience... because... there are more younger ones... It is okay to be younger as long as you are qualified... But there are more qualified ones who have been in the position for longer...yes... because... if you apply the law of localization... there is a no chance that school head... would go out because s/he is living there ... so, s/he could really oversee his/her school ... (P18))

3. Formulated Policies on Hiring, Selection, and Promotion of Principal

The formulated policy was based on the experiences, opinions, and suggestions expressed by the participants. As can be seen on the Figure 1 on the next page, the formulated policy has the following parts: Introduction, Purpose, Scope, and Policies. The policies are classified into the following categories: *Selection Criteria*, *Procedures*, *Duration of Term and Benefits*, and *Principal Empowerment*. The introduction of the policy includes the title of the study, and the background of the study. The purpose and scope stipulate to whom the policy is intended for and the scope of its implementation. Given the fact that the researcher is the principal investigator, the decision for adopting and implementing this policy rests on the persons in authority such as MBHTE Ministry, MSU President, School Directors, Assistant Vice Chancellor, and Division Superintendents. On the other hand, the policies are divided into five categories explains the areas to be evaluated and assessed for the principal applicants: Selection Criteria, Procedures, Duration of Term and Benefits, Developing Principals, and Empowerment.

The *Selection of Criteria* enumerates the basic or minimum requirements to qualify for the position. This includes educational qualifications, experience, and other performance indicators. The *Procedures* vary between the MBHTE and MSU system, whereas the former has six stages while the latter has four phases. Both of these procedures follow the already implemented guidelines of both institutions. The *Duration of Term and Benefits* describes the period of terms of the selected principals and the benefits that come with it, and *their Empowerment* highlight some efforts that the institutions may implement. This is for the selected principal to continuously perform their roles effectively and efficiently. Thus, this policy is drawn from the findings of the study, based on their experiences, perceptions, and suggestions. As recall, the purpose of this paper is to shed light on the hiring process in the MBHTE and MSU System Basic Education Unit and to remediate some problems they echoed.

Figure 1. Formulated Policy of Principal's Selection in the MBHTE and MSU-System Basic Education Units in the BARMM

ACCUMULATION OF PRINCIPALS' SUGGESTIONS:

SELECTION CRITERIA

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add written examination conducted by the MSU System after following the BOR Resolution No. 149, series of 1997. 2. Principal should be the name of designation and not the director and that this should be applied to all basic education units of MSU system. 3. Principals should be empowered in terms of hiring and promoting teachers because they know the ability of their teachers. 4. The university administration is encouraged to provide MOOE to principals for the school maintenance and improvement in its daily operations. 5. Search for principalship should be done after term of designated principals in order to fulfill the desired goals of the principal during his or her term. If a principal is already designated upon a Special Order from the President, the petition should not be entertained and the MSU constituents should respect the discretionary power of the president. | <p>The system follows the BOR Resolution No. 149 Series. 1997 in terms of minimum criteria:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. At least Master's Degree Holder 2. At least Master Teacher in Rank 3. At least two years of teaching experience in the unit where he or she is nominated 4. Permanent Tenure Status / Eligible 5. Returning Grantees must have at least two years teaching service before he or she can be nominated. <p>In this case:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. If there is no one who meets the minimum criteria, the chair of the search committee should not endorse to the President any candidate. Instead, select one of the teachers who meet the minimum criteria in other nearest units to be designated. 2. Prioritize assistant principals who have been in the service for a minimum of 2 years 3. Should consider the length of service by considering seniority; however, he or she should meet the minimum criteria. 4. Should have the ability to handle pressure and obstacles within the community. 5. Should pass the examination given by the system. 6. The detailed concept plan should be valid in one term (four – six years), and this will be monitored annually. |
|---|---|

PROCEDURE

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The university administration is encouraged to provide MOOE to principals for the school maintenance and improvement in its daily operations. 5. Search for principalship should be done after term of designated principals in order to fulfill the desired goals of the principal during his or her term. If a principal is already designated upon a Special Order from the President, the petition should not be entertained and the MSU constituents should respect the discretionary power of the president. | <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add written examination conducted by the MSU System after following the BOR Resolution No. 149, series of 1997.
The four phases in the BOR Resolution No. 149, Series 1997
Phase 1 (Selection of Nominees)
Phase 2 (Selection of Top Five Nominees)
Phase 3 (Semantic Differential and Interview of Top Five)
Phase 4 (Submission of Top Three Finalists to the President) 2. Should pass any national examinations for administrators such as NQESH, CESE, or CESO depending on the level of their positions. 3. If non-passer, there should have principal examination given by the MSU System. The exam should compose of both objective and subjective types. 4. The search for principalship must be done after four – six years. |
|--|--|

DURATION OF TERM AND BENEFITS

1. The one term of principal should be four - six years long.
2. There should be a principal shift, and rotation among qualified aspirants.
3. The honorarium should be increased (or minimum) to six thousand pesos (P6,000.00); this honorarium must not be used for school maintenance and operations.
4. The designated principals should be provided with School Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE), subject to availability of funds.
5. Strictly observing transparency by having detailed liquidation after school academic year through power point presentation.
6. Provide improvement such as buildings and chairs.
7. Land donors should be secured by the MSU System legally.

PRINCIPAL EMPOWERMENT

1. The principal to be included in the panel committee for the hiring or promotion of teachers and to be included in the committee for search for principalship.
2. The principal to have the power to terminate or disregard any petition to replace a designated principal.
3. Principal is the name of their designation to maintain consistency (coordinator and director should be terminated either internal or external units)
4. Respect discretionary power of the president

ACCUMULATION OF PRINCIPALS'
SUGGESTIONS:

1. The Officer-In-Charge or Teacher-In-Charge of the school should be given priority to be promoted over applicants who are classroom teachers. The track record of the school heads should be considered, looking into aspects of whether they have the ability, capabilities, or readiness to manage and lead a secondary school. For instance, the applicants may present an accomplished report demonstrating the various roles they played and accomplished being an OIC, TIC or assistant principal.
2. It is recommended that the committee on hiring principals should follow the educational qualifications and experiences of the applicants, adhering strictly to the policies. This means that the guidelines from DepEd should be followed or be adapted. In this way, unethical practices such as nepotism, favoritism, cronyism, or kinship can be avoided, if not abolished. Moreover, the officials in the higher ups should investigate any reports of bribery or unethical practices and that legal sanctions in accordance with the law, should be imposed upon the individuals.
3. In terms of procurement of their pertinent papers, it is recommended that late applicants should not be entertained regardless of their backing; and this should be passed on the division level first in order to observe efficiency of time processing of the vacant position of the itemized principals.
4. Localization in choosing principals is also recommended. This means that the principals should live within the community they work with. Likewise, they should be native in that place to avoid miscommunication within that area. Possibly, the principal should have the ability to handle their community as well.
5. The principal selection is recommended pass the qualifying exam for principals

1. Adopt the basic policies of Revised Guidelines on Selection, Promotion, And Designation of School Heads (See Appendix B) and Modified Qualification Standards for PI – PIV (See DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2007).
 - Entertain only the aspirants who served or has been serving as Teacher-In-Charge, Officer-In-Charge, Head Teachers, and Assistant Principals for at least 2-5 years beyond.
2. Should have at least master's degree related to the job. Units are also entertained. More specially has doctoral degree (PhD / EdD / Units)
 1. Should have attended seminars, trainings, or workshops related on the job. Preferably, the programs must be conducted by the NEAP or any National or International Program.
 2. Should be Teacher III or Master Teacher in position to consider length of experience and service. However, if Teacher I, at least designated as school head for five (5) years (Teacher-In-Charge, Officer-In-Charge, Head Teacher, Assistant Principal) and must be at least ten (10) years in teaching service.
 3. Should have the ability to connect within the weakness and strength of the community.
 4. Should pass the various type of examinations given by the region (Objective and Subjective Type) or national (NQESH).
 5. Must pass the interview process related to the job.
 6. Must present a detailed agenda (Concept paper for MSU) for Five years as aspirants.
 7. If there is no one who meet the minimum criteria, aspirants should not be entertained and another call for principal promotion should be published.

PROCEDURE

Selection Stage 1:

The division will do the screening in terms of meeting the minimum criteria of aspirants. Such as:

- Qualifications / Eligibility
- Managerial Degree, Experiences, Seminars and Trainings
- NQESH passer
- Agenda (Plan)

Note: Do not accept late submission of pertinent papers (ranking will be posted)

Selection Stage 2:

Division will conduct examination (division level) for the principal aspirants. NQESH Passers are exempted.

Note: Examination type must be objective and subjective type related to the job.

(Passers will be posted)

Selection Stage 3:

Those who will pass the Division Level Examination or NQESH will be subjected to interview and presentation of school's agenda.

(Passers will be posted)

Selection Stage 4:

Selected passer aspirants will be endorsed by the division to the region for further screening.

(Passers will be posted)

Selection Stage 5:

There will be Regional Examination except for NQESH passers.

(Passers will be posted)

Note: Examination type must be objective and subjective type related to the job.

- from division level, region level, and national level such as the NQESH before they can be promoted as full-fledge principal. The examination is recommended to be both objective and subjective type.
6. It is recommended that principals be empowered in terms of promoting teachers because they are the one who have known the capacity and ability of their teachers; as well as the subject teachers that deserved to be promoted. This suggestion could also lessen the delay of hiring of teachers and fast track the process.
 7. A more transparent selection process for principal is recommended by publishing or releasing the results of the ranking.
 8. Lastly, the principals are commended to practice and apply Islamic beliefs and values and that respect for one's religious beliefs and culture must be upheld.

Selection Stage 6:

Passers are subjected to regional interview process.
(Passers will be posted)

Selection Stage 7:

Top finalists will be endorsed to the Office of Minister (full-pledged principals should be posted)

DURATION OF TERM AND BENEFITS

1. Adopts the National Process: ITEMIZED
2. Reshuffle the principals every three years by letting the innovative principals handle the unprogressive schools.
3. No honorarium (as salary is more than enough)
4. Adopts the MOOE process. However, there should be an annual detailed liquidation after school academic year through (PPT) presentation of the school activities and expenses. Everything must be documented.

PRINCIPAL EMPOWERMENT

1. The principal shall have the power to endorse or recommend an applicant for the principal position to the division.
2. The Division to endorse the teacher aspirants to the region after evaluation and screening. (hired teachers before school academic year)
3. There must be legal action upon witnessing of bribery.
4. The principal shall be given the authority to recommend applicants to immediately fill in natural vacancies of principals and (especially) teachers to avoid hiring of volunteers before the academic year.
5. The principal must practice Islamic views; however, if the principal is non-Muslims, he must respect the Islamic rules and regulation within the region. The superior must respect the principals and treat them fairly regardless of tribes or religion.

DISCUSSION

1. Perception of the Principal Selection Process

1.1 Perception of Group A – MSU

The criteria consistently mentioned by the participants are all found in the BOR Resolution No. 149, series of 1997 that their scheme consists of Phase 1 to 4, which implies that the applicants do have to go through a meticulous screening process. As Huber and Hiltmann (2010) concluded the German School system that the legal basis for the selection and appointment of school leaders is within the responsibility of the respective state as well and is formulated in its respective laws. The participants' opinion on the consistent and good hiring procedures in MSU basic units suggests that principals value a standardized approach to the hiring process. This likely includes consistent application of selection criteria, interview processes, and evaluation methods. By having consistent procedures, principals may feel that the process is fairer and more transparent, which can lead to greater trust among stakeholders, including staff, parents, and the community. This trust is crucial for maintaining a positive school culture and ensuring that the best candidates are selected for positions. Furthermore, the theme "good hiring process" implies that the participants from MSU have positive perceptions towards the process as a whole, they believe it is well-structured, organized, and effective. This positive perception can contribute to a more positive work environment, as the principals are more likely to be satisfied with a process they perceive as fair and effective.

Furthermore, the findings in the category *Effective and High Performing Unit Due to Constituents*, suggested that MSU principals believe that the hiring process plays a crucial role in the effectiveness and performance of their unit, which may refer to their school or department. These principals feel that hiring the right people with the necessary skills, experience, and values and impact to the community can lead to a more cohesive team that is better equipped to achieve the school's goals. This highlights the importance of a rigorous and well-thought-out hiring process in building a high-performing organization. As revealed by the DepEd Order No. 19, s. 2022 which was released to establish a competency-based Agency Merit Selection Plan to ensure that in all governance levels the department hires and retains the right people for the right job at the time, by strictly adhering to the principles of merit, fitness, competence, equal opportunity, transparency, and accountability. The Merit Selection plan is a systematic method of assessing and selecting employees on the basis of their relative qualifications and competence to perform the duties and responsibilities of the position. The Plan covers career positions in the first, second and third levels in the DepEd whether teaching or non-teaching. It may also include non-career positions (Llego, 2002).

On the other hand, the category *Nomination and Replacement Process* suggested a fair process because their view of their procedure is positive. It also recommends allowing other eligible candidates to take the lead, which would make the process more alluring. As Llego (2023) further stated that selection of employees for appointment in the DepEd shall be anchored on the principles of merit, competence, fitness, and equality. It shall be open to all who are qualified, regardless of gender, civil status, disability, religion, ethnicity, or political affiliation. When a position in the first, second or third level becomes vacant, applicants for appointment who are competent, qualified and possess appropriate civil service eligibility shall be considered for permanent appointment.

Generally, the principals' perception of problems in the search process, particularly when a newly installed principal will have to be immediately replaced because of some factors, like having a new president, indicates that they face challenges in finding suitable candidates for positions and their need for a principal who can sustain and finish what has been started. This could be due to various factors, such as a limited pool of qualified applicants, specific job requirements that are hard to fill, or external factors that impact the availability of candidates. Addressing these challenges may require efforts to broaden the applicant pool, revise job requirements, or provide additional support for recruitment efforts.

On the other hand, their perception and mention of the absence of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) implies that MSU principals may feel that inadequate resources impact the hiring process or the overall functioning of the school. Addressing these resource constraints may be necessary to ensure that the hiring process and the hired principal is effective and that schools can attract and retain qualified staff. Having said all of that, MSU principals' perceptions of the hiring process reflect the importance of consistency, transparency, effectiveness, and adequate resources in ensuring that the best candidates are selected for positions. Addressing these findings

can help improve the hiring process and contribute to the overall effectiveness and performance of schools.

On a positive side, the principals from MSU-SBEU generally appreciated the existing process. There is consistency in following the selection process, but they are not quite satisfied with its transparency and other aspects. It can be therefore said that even though they have expressed good opinions regarding hiring selection not only the principals but also the teachers, however, some problems need to be addressed in the system, especially the absence of MOOE. In this manner, the administration might have neglected to look beyond what is important in managing schools. Thus, the MSU system may provide maintenance and support financially for improving school structure and other expenditure that needs sustenance. They should not rely alone on the financial support of local governments because sometimes this is not available. This finding is supported by the social exchange theory which means that there must be expectation of having benefits after the service they rendered in the school and its people. It does not mean that the sustenance is the benefits that must be rewarded to them, but instead this serves as their external motivation to fully implement their main goal as a principal; because there is evident that sometimes no one wants to run as principal because of the many challenges. It entails in leading a school that has no identified maintenance. In fact, without maintenance, the organization could not function. Ultimately, the leader's interest in enhancing the school plant could stem from this maintenance. As Cook et al. (2013) mentioned that Homans' key propositions framed the study of social behavior in terms of rewards and punishments. Behavior that is rewarded in general continues (up to the limit of diminishing marginal utility). His first proposition, the *success proposition*, states that behavior that generates positive consequences is likely to be repeated. The second proposition, the *stimulus proposition*, states that behavior that has been rewarded on such occasions in the past will be performed in similar situations. The *value proposition*, the third proposition, specifies that the more valuable the result of an action to an actor, the more likely that action is to be performed.

1.2 Perception of Group B – MBHTE

The findings in the first category *There is a Fair Process* entail a positive perception among the principals as to the hiring process in MBHTE. With them attesting that there is no bribery and that the applicants are promoted based on their qualifications is an indication of the integrity of the process, its transparency, and effectiveness. This process brings more confidence for the applicants with the belief that they can be promoted provided that they meet or surpass the selection criteria and are highly qualified. As Karim et al. (2021) mentioned that every employer in the organization is required to advocate for and carry out the recruiting and selection process in a very special manner. The qualified workforce is essential to the organization's success and has a direct bearing on organizational performance. Efficient recruitment and selection procedures are essential to any firm, just as financial resources are. The success of appropriate recruiting and selecting processes has a significant impact on the value of human resources. Finding suitable applicants for the organization is the overarching goal of recruiting and selection.

The second category which highlighted that there is a delay in the hiring process is connected to the study of Satul (2001) who concluded that there is a lack of publications in Sulu that can be used to publish vacancies of the Division. Because of the lack of newspapers, vacancies cannot be known to the greatest number of applicants. Only through letters, word of mouth and bulletins that vacancies were disseminated. Due to this limited dissemination of the vacancies, the division is deprived of attracting the best professionals who may apply in the Division. Notably, the delay in the hiring process due to the process of centralization implies the opinion of the participants for decentralization and contextualization of the procedures. A delay, slow, or centralize hiring procedures tend to be prone or has more potential for red tape, bureaucracies, or worse corruptions. Besides, it is the distinctive decentralization of decision-making processes in the education sector – besides open enrolment and the accountability of schools to the public – that has had serious effects on the principals' functions and range of tasks (Huber and Hiltmann, 2010).

Indeed, empowering principal is very crucial in achieving high quality of education. As mentioned in the DepEd Order No. 17, s. 1997, the Office hereby adopts a policy of empowering all public elementary and secondary school principals in order to achieve desired higher learning outcomes. All school principals shall henceforth be vested with instructional administrative and fiscal autonomy for a more effective and efficient delivery of quality basic education. Moreover, the notion that instruction is the heart of a teacher's job, then the principals have vital role to play in school improvement (Mendels, 2012).

The findings in the category *Considering Division Level of Selecting principals and Teachers* are related to the various findings of Lee and Mao (2020), one of the depicted identified reviews were superintendents, and hiring practices at the organizational level. Perhaps, the findings indicated that the region would have positive results if it hired applicants at the division level since they are aware of what is going on the ground. After all, Lee and Mao (2020) postulated that the results they can produce will also contribute to building sound policies that impact the recruitment and selection of school principals who are well-positioned and well-prepared to help teachers and students succeed.

In general, the findings in the category "BARMM Decides Everything" indicate that principals in the BARMM region feel that the BARMM has significant control over decision-making processes, including promotions and hiring. Thus, this perception has several implications: first, the mention of cronyism suggests that there may be instances where individuals are promoted based on personal connections rather than merit. This can have negative consequences for the MBHTE, as it may lead to a lack of fairness and transparency in the hiring process. It can also demotivate teachers who feel that they are not being rewarded based on their qualifications and hard work. Second, the reference to the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF) in the process can be problematic as it undermines the integrity of the hiring process or leads to decisions that are not in the best interest of the organization. Thirdly, disclosing that the MBHTE regional director or ministry has the prerogative to decide on promotions suggests that there may be a lack of clear criteria or guidelines for decision-making. This can lead to inconsistencies and perceptions of unfairness among employees. Thus, addressing these issues requires a

commitment to transparency, fairness, and meritocracy in the hiring and promotion processes. By establishing clear criteria, providing training and support for decision-makers, and promoting a culture of fairness and integrity, MBHTE-BARMM can mitigate the negative impacts of external influence and promote a more effective and equitable work environment. This is supported by Casil (2021) who revealed that to set the merit-based recruitment as an ideal or the standard to be realized does not mean that it should be an objective reality. It has previously discussed the useful advantages of meritocracy in enhancing the effectiveness of governance, which can have a significant impact on the Bangsamoro people. Beyond its usefulness, meritocracy adheres to the notion of fairness, which is fundamental to the Bangsamoro struggle.

Moreover, the category *Inconsistency of Hiring and Manipulation of the Process*, this manipulation leads to the perception of the other principals, consistent to what they mentioned earlier, that there is *Palakasan System* or the practice of using someone's connections and backer to get the position. According to some participants, once they have connection can be the principals. It is observed that while some principals attested to the integrity of the hiring process, there are, however, others who substantiated that there actually some external factors who would interfere or manipulate either the process or the final decisions. One study illustrates this point that the cultural values also play a key role to promote a patronage practices. For instance, the respect of authority and elders can lead to nepotism and paternalism. One could also find it difficult to critique problematic cultural norms, since respecting the authority and elders promote more the virtues of obedience than being critical. Aside from the values of respect, Filipino cultural standards like the ethics of 'debt of thanks' (*utang na loob*) and the psycho-social concept of 'shame' (*hiya*) both restrain and enable *padrino* system. One's *utang na loob* (debt of gratitude), and *pakikisama* (friendship or familial ties) could influence the recruitment process in the office or these cultural values lead to accommodating certain people of special treatment (Casil, 2021).

As to the *Prioritizing OIC or who Managed School Already*; possibly, the greatest way to honor OIC principals' struggles is to prioritize them because, given their role as administrators, they have already gained experience as transformative leaders. This theory has a great-implication on this study by knowing how the selected principals supervise and manage the subordinates within the organization. Since the principals who manage schools are being chosen purposively or being nominated as aspirants. Among all the styles, this touches the employees or subordinates by motivating them intrinsically or even extrinsically and by utilizing charismatic and virtue behavior. In short, this leadership styles could be one of the best criteria in selecting the principals which is connected to the other criteria wherein an applicant must have experienced managing a school or have taken on a school leader role. According to Bass and Riggio (2006), transformational leadership has rapidly become the approach of choice for much of the research and application of leadership theory. In many ways, transformational leadership has captured the imagination of scholars, of noted practitioners, and of students of leadership.

The category, *Imposing Transparency*, suggests that principals are advocating for greater openness and accountability in the hiring process. The participants' suggestion to post the results of principal hiring publicly aimed to increase transparency and accountability. By making the results available to all applicants, it reduces the likelihood of manipulation or favoritism in the selection process. It also allows applicants to understand how the decision was made and provides them with an opportunity to seek clarification or appeal if necessary. Disclosure of promotion results becomes more transparent and fairer. This practice is also seen as a way to align with practices observed in other divisions, indicating a desire for consistency and fairness across the region. From this finding, it can be implied that there is a need for BARMM to implement transparency measures to increase accountability among decision-makers. When the hiring process is open and results are publicly available, decision-makers are more likely to adhere to fair and objective criteria. Moreover, transparent hiring practices can help build trust among stakeholders, including applicants, current employees, and the community. When the process is perceived as fair, individuals are more likely to trust the decisions made by the organization. Likewise, Aziz and Quraishi (2016) revealed that more inclusive and transparent selection processes need to be evolved to select appropriate persons as principals and school leaders.

The result in the category *Hardship of being OIC* shows that all OIC principals should be valued because they do all principal duties but receiving different pay. In fact, Division Memorandum No. 98, s. 2019 specified that the OIC-Principals are expected to spearhead in setting the direction and strategy of the school through efficiently and transparently managing the fiscal and asset resources of the school and to facilitate organizational management through coaching, mentoring, and instruction supervision of school staff. The OIC-Principal must also foster a child-friendly, safe, and conducive environment in the teaching-learning process while maintaining and implementing standards and disciplinary systems for both teachers and learners. Applicants for OIC-Principal must encourage shared governance of the school with internal and external stakeholders and is accountable for the learning outcomes of the school.

Furthermore, the result in the category *Filling in the Vacant Items Immediately* is parallel to the study of Pantoja and de Castro (2023) who revealed top three (3) problems encountered by the participants in the Implementation of the Recruitment, Selection and Promotion (RSP): First: It took them a long time to be hired for permanent vacant positions and be promoted to the next higher position. Second: The time needed to comply with needed requirements or documents was short. Third: Interview was difficult. As an output of the study, it may serve as a reference guide per LGU, which also has its own Merit Selection plan (MSP). Indeed, reclassification could be used to solve this issue regarding vacant items. As Llego (2018) disclosed that there is no vacant item once the item is reclassified. Lastly, reclassification may only be allowed after three (3) consecutive years of at least Very Satisfactory or two (2) consecutive years of Outstanding Performance from the effectivity of the latest appointment. Legally, based on the DepEd Order No. 97, s. 2011, the Secretary of Education shall create a promotions board, at the appropriate levels, which shall formulate the implement a system of promotion for schools' division supervisors, schools' heads shall be based on educational qualification, merit, and

performance rather than on the number of teachers/learning facilitators and learners in the school.

The perceptions of the principals from MBHTE-BARMM indicates their call for more transparent, consistent, and empowered group of people who are tasked to select and promote qualified principals. These perceptions are arguably rooted in their frustrations from the challenges and problems they encountered upon applying for the principal position. From an educational point of view that aims to attain a better literacy rate, good academic performance, and student learning outcomes, hiring process for principalship needs to comply with the standard-based qualifications in accordance with the policies of the Department of Education. In this way, the school heads and the education agency can ensure that the programs of the department can be properly, efficiently and effectively implemented because schools are managed by a leader who were chosen based on meritocracy. This claim is supported by AISheihhi and Alzouebi (2020) from United Arab Emirates, who cited that the school principals play an imperative role in supporting the school, staff, and student performance, and therefore it is extremely important to create a clear, transparent and effective hiring policies in order to hire the most competent, effective and best performing school principals to lead the educational reform process.

As can be seen between the categories generated from both groups, there are differences as to their opinions and it shows that principals from MSU have more positive perceptions than the principals from MBHTE. Nevertheless, both groups expressed positive attitudes or perceptions toward their respective hiring process and at the same time mentioned some negative aspects of it. From these negative perceptions, the participants conversely offered some suggestions that may help improve the mechanism of selecting or promoting principals. Both groups expressed fair process, but there were some who of inconsistencies in the process. Some of the suggestions from the principals, particularly from MBHTE, they suggested that division superintendents and schools should play a role or be part of the decision makers and the process of promotion, this means that they want the hiring or selection process be decentralized from regional level to division level. Moreover, they suggested to prioritize promoting school heads who took on the role of OIC or TIC because of their experience and have already invested efforts for their schools. Ultimately, both sets of principals called for a more transparent and consistent hiring process that is equal for everyone and that principals who will be chosen should be strictly based on their qualifications and not with the influence of some external factors, especially if the hired principal is not even qualified and did not go through the process. This conclusion regarding inconsistency is complemented with the study of Khumalo (2021) who indicated that there were mixed reactions on the allegations of the selling of vacancies in schools. The officials who joined in the Department of Basic Education (DBE) investigation indicates that there is evidence of wrongdoing in the recruitment and appointment processes. Moreover, it can be argued and concluded that there is evidence of the selling of posts. Certainly, there are always wrongdoings faced in every organization which cannot be prevented. Thus, this region should practice decentralization not because they know the applicants but because they know who are

dedicated and devoted applicants. In fact, the role of the leaders has great impact in achieving quality education (Day & Sammons, 2016).

2. Suggestion on how to Improve the Hiring Selection

2.1 Suggestion on how to Improve the Hiring Selection of Group A – MSU-System Basic Education Unit

The suggestion (*Principal Empowerment*) of the participants to principals should be empowered in their functions is significant for educational policy and practice. Empowering principals can lead to several benefits such as being better equipped to make effective decisions that can enhance overall school performance, including teacher hiring, academic achievement and student outcomes. When principals are empowered, they are more likely to demonstrate effective leadership behaviors, such as fostering a positive school climate, promoting professional development, and implementing innovative practices for teachers and students. Hence, it should be emphasized that empowering school principals can have a positive impact on school effectiveness and its stakeholders as a whole, consequently these could contribute into improved educational outcomes.

The participants suggestion to be granted MOOE for the principal, which will be spent for school maintenance and operations, implies two things: first, their schools need a lot of improvements for repairs or maintenance or purchase of things that their teachers and students need, on the other hand, the idea that they have been requesting this and were not able to be granted until now means that the administration may have not sufficient budget to be allotted to all their basic education units. Given the budget provided by the national government to the Mindanao State University against its high number of employees, campuses, and basic education schools; it might be quite challenging for the administration to request for additional budget in the congress. This suggested that the MSU-System Basic Education Unit places a high value on MOOE.

The results indicate that the president is treated with the utmost respect, which is an indication of a good rapport with the chief executive officer. This is similar to the German school system, which is under federal control. At a national level, independence in matters of education and culture lies with each state due to the federal principle. This means that each of the 16 federal states (the German Länder) has an individual school system ensured by jurisdictional and administrative laws. Hence, the legal basis for the selection and appointment of school leaders is within the responsibility of the respective state as well and is formulated in its respective laws (Huber and Hiltmann, 2010).

These suggestions for additional technical requirements in the search for principalship imply that there are aspects to the mechanism that have to be addressed to ensure that highly qualified applicants are designated. As Aravena (2020) revealed that the first is eliminatory in which candidates have to prove their knowledge and competencies through university administered written exams. These tests measure the following: (1) specific pedagogical knowledge, (2) critical reading skills, (3) management,

administrative and financial knowledge (4) academic management and (5) psycho-technical abilities. Next, the candidate's academic and professional backgrounds are validated in an interview conducted by an expert in school administration and management.

It can be argued despite the perceptions of some principals that the hiring process of MSU-SBEU is good and consistent, there are still some issues that need to be addressed based on their experiences. This led to a strong call for the higher ups to revisit the guidelines in the search for principalship and allow more meticulous and fair procedures of hiring because ultimately, the schools will benefit for a highly qualified school leader. This is coordinated to the study of Aziz and Quraishi (2016) who revealed that more inclusive and transparent selection processes need to be evolved to select appropriate persons as principals and school leaders.

Ultimately, everything within the organization is managed by the principals. As Farley-Ripple et al. (2012) postulated that to achieve great schools, there is a need for great leaders, and calls for improvement have raised the stakes – and responsibilities – for those who work to lead schools toward success. Moreover, the understanding of the significance of administrative leadership grows, the recruiting, developing, supporting, and retaining quality leaders are vital to both local and national reform movements. Furthermore, Huber and Hiltmann (2010) argued the school division of the Ministry of Education should ensure that schools are effectively managed and that the education provided is in accordance with national objectives. Nevertheless, Crow (2006) postulated that along with evidence of the importance of the principalship has come the recognition that the principal's role has changed within an increasingly high stakes policy environment.

2.2 Suggestion on how to Improve the Hiring Selection of Group B - MBHTE

Considering Length and Managerial Experience implied best process because they considered first the managerial experiences of the principal applicants. This is similar to the key points of Atherton (2018) that there were positive relationships between discipline incidents and number of schools and practices such as minority applicant recruitment, crafted job description, administrative experience, and effective leadership applicant.

Certainly, *Principal Empowerment* is a good suggestion because they are aware of what is happening in the field. As Isa et al. (2024) suggested that involvement of school principals in planning instructional programs and activities would make them cooperate with the administration in achieving the desired educational goals. However, the extent and level of principal's empowerment in decision-making is affected by their socio-demographic and academic factors. Moreover, this hopes to shed light on importance of promoting a culture of professional development that will prepare principals to confront education challenges and obstacles brought about by the dynamics of the 21st century education landscape.

The suggestion to *Adopt the National Guidelines* implies that there may have been inconsistencies or deviations from the national guidelines in the past, leading to a call for stricter adherence to ensure fairness and transparency in the selection process. Moreover, consistent to what this paper has been reiterating, that there is a need for recognition of the role that qualifications and examinations play in determining the suitability of candidates for principal positions. This is to ensure that school leaders possess the necessary skills, knowledge, and competencies to effectively lead schools. On the other hand, the reference to moral governance by P15 highlights the cultural and ethical considerations that are important in the context of the BARMM. This suggests a desire to align the selection and promotion of school principals with the values and principles of the local community, particularly in relation to Islamic principles of governance. The acknowledgment that the BARMM has used the national guidelines but has failed to strictly follow them suggests a need for improved implementation and monitoring mechanisms. This implies that there may be challenges or gaps in the current implementation process that need to be addressed to ensure that the guidelines are followed consistently and effectively. In general, the findings suggest a need for greater adherence to national guidelines, a focus on qualifications and examinations, consideration of ethical and cultural values, and improved implementation and monitoring mechanisms in the selection and promotion of school principals in the BARMM.

This is a smart move, as *New Leaders for New Schools* (2009) made clear that principals need special attitudes, aptitudes, and values. The following qualities are encouraged in candidates: the unwavering belief that every student can succeed academically; the instructional expertise to lead a staff; the capacity to manage others well; the skill and orientation to use student learning data to drive breakthrough gains; and the operational skills to run the school day-to-day in a way that frees up the principal to concentrate on enhancing instruction and fostering a culture within the school. Organization should ensure that all turnaround principals demonstrate a strong interest in and ability to implement the high-level principal actions and school-wide practices known to spur breakthrough results in challenging schools. Also, to ensure that they are prepared to take the difficult actions necessary to build a staff that is aligned to these goals.

The results *Considering Qualification and Personal Quality* are similar to the finding of Rattley (2016) who also indicated that the participants placed more emphasis on certain competencies than others. Based on participant perspectives, two competencies associated with turnaround principals emerged: belief in children and job affinity. Nevertheless, the importance of educational qualifications is paramount and basic requirement that cannot be disregarded in any aspects of promotion or hiring. The findings suggest that MBHTE principals value educational qualifications, professional and personal competence, and qualifying exams as important factors in determining the suitability of individuals for the role of school principals. These are supported by the DepEd Order No. 19, s. 2022, that the Merit Selection plan is a systematic method of assessing and selecting employees on the basis of their relative qualifications and competence to perform the duties and responsibilities of the position. The Plan covers career positions in the first, second and third levels in the DepEd whether teaching or

non-teaching. It may also include non-career positions (Llego, 2002). On the other hand, this also implies that there is an existing unfairness in the hiring process, meaning there are principals who were selected without meeting the qualifications. These factors are seen as essential for ensuring that principals are well-prepared to lead schools effectively and meet the challenges of the education sector.

The findings on *Considering Consistency of Process* suggest a strong emphasis on transparency, fairness, and equality in the selection process for school principals. Participants view these principles as essential for ensuring that the best candidates are selected, and that the integrity of the selection process is maintained. The findings are supported by the DepEd Order No. 19, s. 2022, which was released to establish a competency-based Agency Merit Selection Plan to ensure that in all governance levels the department hires and retains the right people for the right job at the time, by strictly adhering to the principles of merit, fitness, competence, equal opportunity, transparency, and accountability (Llego, 2002).

The findings on considering the *Importance of Community and Linkages* entail several implications. Firstly, that the MBHTE principals who live in the community can be more involved in the day-to-day operations of the school and can be more responsive to the needs of the school community. The involvement of political leaders implies a belief that political leaders have a role to play in ensuring that schools are well-managed and that vacancies are filled in a timely and effective manner. The MBHTE principals also believe that principals should embody the cultural and ethical values of the local community, particularly in a Muslim-majority region like the BARMM. Therefore, the findings entail a strong emphasis on the importance of community connection, localization, and the practice of cultural and ethical values in the selection and assignment of school principals in the BARMM. Participants view these factors as essential for ensuring that principals are effective leaders who can meet the needs of the local community. As Akinbode and Al Shuhumi (2018) postulated that it is compulsory for the school to change its content of study as well as process of study to match the contemporary need of the community it serves. This task lies on the principal, who leads and guides teachers towards realizing the school vision and mission.

Similarly, Vygotsky strongly believed that community plays a central role in the process of “making meaning.” Cognitive development is a socially mediated process in which children acquire cultural values, beliefs, and problem-solving strategies through collaborative dialogues with more knowledgeable members of society (Mcleod, 2024). To elaborate more, Burr (2015) explained that social constructionism can be thought of as a theoretical orientation which, to a greater or lesser degree, underpins all of these newer approaches, which are currently offering radical and critical alternatives in psychology and social psychology, as well as in other disciplines in the social sciences and humanities. In this vein, this theory helps this study explore how social and cultural factors influence the selection of secondary principals in the BARMM region by considering its impact of community values and expectations on the process. This includes the potential involvement of nepotism, connections, friendship, or favoritism in the process of hiring principals.

Mainly, a closer analysis of these two sets of principals depicts that both groups call for empowerment of the principals in the processes and decision making, specifically, in terms of hiring and promotions of their teachers. Principals from MSU underscores the need to be provided with school maintenance because of difficulty in operating without expenditures. Likewise, there are some requirements that they wanted to be included in the criteria, such as inclusion of written examination, sticking of the criteria solely by not designating the non-passers, and by not entertaining petition when the principals are already designated because they are already undergone with process and of course these principals are already chosen by the president as he has discretionary power. Hence, they suggested to respect the decision of the appointing authority.

For the MBHTE principals in Group B, they have more varied suggestions, nonetheless, they all pointed out for the need to be transparent, credible, fair, and to strictly adhere to the national guidelines in hiring. Though it is stipulated on the standard qualification of civil service the importance of experiences and qualifications; the MBHTE principals highlighted a firm implementation of this policy because for them, qualification such as MA or PhD holder may not suffice as indicators of competence and abilities of a school head to lead a school. Thus, they suggested a comprehensive assessment of principal applicants by conducting both objective and subjective type of test, which includes an essay type of examination. Finally, both sets of principals recommended the considerations of community linkages and practices; this means principals must know how to handle and respect the community members, which includes that it is an advantage if the applicant is living within the area of school.

The discoveries are parallel to Romanowski et al. (2019) who provided insights into the principal selection process and demonstrated the following: that principals should develop their decision-making skills, should advance as instructional leaders and, since government schools are very diverse, principals must be able to manage issues of nationality, culture and equality.

Conclusions

The principals' perceptions regarding the selection process, generally, both groups expressed positive perceptions in terms of the selection criteria and the procedures. However, their negative perceptions stem from the practices that deviate from the standard procedures. These are factors that internally and externally affect or influence of the hiring procedures, factors such as political involvement, *palakasan* system, designated or appointed based on connections and not the qualifications, and the transparency of the results of the hiring process. Meanwhile, the MSU principals complained of the lack of MOOE given to the principals. Therefore, it can be inferred that while principals acknowledge the importance of fair and transparent hiring processes, there are significant challenges posed by external influences and insufficient resource allocation. Addressing these issues is crucial for ensuring the integrity and effectiveness of the selection process in educational institutions.

Meanwhile, policy suggested by the principals for the improvement of the hiring process, common to both groups is their call for empowerment of the principals. They call for the principals to be given authority to be part of the hiring or recruitment of teachers, and be allowed to recommend a potential applicant for the principal. Specific to MSU principals is their sentiment to be given budget for the operation, maintenance and other expenses of the school in order for them to effectively function and implement programs. Meanwhile, specific to MBHTE principals are their suggestions for transparency and consistency of the stipulated guidelines and procedures of appointing and selection of principals. Thus, it can be inferred that principals are calling for reforms in BARMM that would give them more control over staffing decisions, adequate funding for school operations, and transparent and consistent guidelines for appointing principals, and even teachers. These recommendations aim to improve the overall effectiveness and efficiency of the hiring process in educational institutions.

From these findings on the perceptions and suggestions of the participants with regards to the hiring process in BARMM as a whole, it can be concluded that there is an imperative need to update and make reforms in the processes of hiring both in MSU and MBHTE. Thus, the policy formulated in this study address these pressing needs and problems of the hiring process in BARMM. This formulated policy is holistic and contextualized to suit the specific needs of BARMM constituents. Knowing the unique social, cultural, religious, and political underpinnings of BARMM as a region, it is only fitting that policy guidelines on hiring, promotion, appointment, and selection of principals or employees, in general, must be designed, implemented, and evaluated. Moreover, this study adds to the growing body of knowledge on policy-based studies that explore educational or school leadership, educational management, and policy-making investigations. Specifically, this present study shed light on the dynamics and complex mechanisms of hiring and selecting teachers in the BARMM region, this is juxtaposed with the common practices that apparently depart from the standard protocols. The formulated policy of principal selection can be further studied or adopted by policy makers and education authorities, specifically in BARMM.

Recommendations

The accumulation of suggested policy presented in the formulated policy are some actions that can be taken to address some problems that were shared by the principals; and in this part are the recommended individuals or concern persons who can implement these recommendations. Primary, to empower principals in hiring and promoting teachers, the Superintendents and Assistant Vice-Chief of Academic Affairs should suggest policy changes. In this manner, Superintendents should recommend hiring and promoting papers to the division office, while Assistant Vice-Chiefs should advocate for the president by adapting suggestions to empower principals. This will improve the hiring and promotion process in the region. Furthermore, this should be scrutinized by Regional Directors in the Basic Education, MSU Presidents, Human Resources and Management Division Boards, and the Minister of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education. Also, the regional government and local government units are encouraged to propose the policy nationally to support the educational goals of the BARMM region. Lastly, Future

researchers may use a quantitative approach to corroborate the findings and examine the challenges faced by principals and HR members in developing their skills and knowledge.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured the confidentiality of the principals' experiences, opinions, and ideas. Verbal and written consent was obtained from the participants and from the school division superintendents of the said region before the interview process (optional only since there is BARMM Letter as a whole). Prior to the interview, participants received a letter of consent, a confidentiality agreement, and an explanation of the dissertation. To protect their privacy, codenames such as P1 – P25 are used in MBHTE and M1-M11 were utilized for the MSU-System participants, while the human resources personnels were assigned HR1 and HR2 codenames. The selected principals and human resources personnel were informed that they have the right to withdraw from the interview at any time. The interview process was stress-free for the participants.

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